

Invited talk

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17532339>

BUILDING TRUST IN AI: THE ROLE OF ETHICS, REGULATION, AND TECHNOLOG

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Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Generative AI in particular, holds immense transformative potential, but it also presents serious challenges related to bias, opacity, and misuse. This talk will examine how such risks can be mitigated through a combination of technical safeguards, ethical frameworks, and regulatory measures. It will emphasize the intersection of technology, law, and ethics, with a focus on governance models such as the EU AI Act. The talk will also introduce the Circle U. Knowledge Hub on AI, which supports this mission by advancing human-centered, inclusive, and equitable AI and promoting systems that are ethical, safe, trustworthy, and sustainable.